

Clinicopathological Assessment of Cervical Lymphadenopathy among the Patients Attending a Tertiary Care Centre in Assam**M. K. Mili¹, Mubeez Mustafa Badusha², Krishna Pegu³, Rupanjita Sangma⁴, Aditya Sharma⁵, Hironya Borah⁶**¹Associate Professor, Department of ENT, Assam Medical College, Dibrugarh, Assam²Senior Resident, Department of ENT, Lakhimpur Medical College, Chowkham, Assam³Assistant Professor, Department of ENT, Lakhimpur Medical College, Chowkham, Assam⁴Professor & Head, Department of ENT, Nagaon Medical College, Nagaon, Assam⁵Professor, Department of Pathology, Assam Medical College, Dibrugarh, Assam⁶Professor & Head, Department of ENT, Lakhimpur Medical College, Chowkham, Assam

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Abstract

Background: Cervical lymphadenopathy is a common and complex condition that can manifest as a local or systemic pathology, ranging from minor infections to life-threatening malignancies. Accurate diagnosis and management of cervical lymphadenopathy are crucial, as persistent and painless swelling of neck nodes can be a warning sign for serious conditions such as tuberculosis, cancer, and lymphoma. This study aims to investigate the clinical profile of patients presenting with cervical lymphadenopathy and correlate clinical diagnosis with pathological findings.

Materials and Methods: A hospital-based observational study investigated the clinicopathological profile of cervical lymphadenopathy in patients attending the Department of Otorhinolaryngology, Assam Medical College & Hospital, and Dibrugarh for one year from March 2023 to February 2024. A total of 50 patients with cervical lymphadenopathy were enrolled, with a focus on symptoms, lymph node involvement, and diagnostic methods including clinical examination, fine-needle aspiration cytology (FNAC), and biopsy.

Results: The majority of patients were males (58%), with a mean age of 36.86 years, and presented with unilateral cervical lymph node involvement (80%) and single lymph node enlargement (60%). Tuberculous lymphadenitis was the most common diagnosis (56%), followed by metastatic secondaries (20%), reactive lymphadenitis (10%), Hodgkin's lymphoma (4%), non-Hodgkin's lymphoma (4%) and granulomatous lymphadenitis (6%). Fine-needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) showed high diagnostic accuracy for tuberculous lymphadenitis, reactive lymphadenitis, and secondaries outperforming clinical diagnosis alone.

Conclusion: This study highlights the importance of cervical lymphadenopathy as an indicator of underlying conditions, with tuberculous lymphadenitis being the most common cause in the Indian population. Fine-needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) and open biopsy with histopathological examination are essential diagnostic tools, enabling early detection and referral, particularly in resource-limited primary healthcare settings. The findings of this study can inform healthcare strategies to reduce diagnostic delays and improve treatment outcomes for tuberculosis and lymph node cancers.

Keywords: Cervical Lymphadenopathy, FNAC, Histopathological Examination.

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Introduction

Cervical lymphadenopathy is a frequently encountered medical condition by any clinician, especially otorhinolaryngologists. It may be the manifestation of a local pathology or a systemic pathology ranging from the minor infective etiology to life threatening malignant condition. Lymphadenopathy means having one or more lymph nodes that are bigger, abnormal consistency, or are more numerous than usual. [1] A persistent and painless swelling of the neck nodes indicate a

warning sign for various serious conditions, including tuberculosis (in both children and adults), cancer (particularly in elderly individuals), and lymphoma. These conditions can cause enlargement of the cervical lymph nodes without causing pain, making it essential to investigate further to determine the underlying cause. [2] A thorough medical history and further investigation are crucial to determine the underlying cause. [3] FNAC is the preferred first-line diagnostic test for

evaluating cervical lymphadenopathy. A lymph node biopsy, specifically of the most affected node, is usually needed for a clear diagnosis. [4]

Aims and Objectives

1. To study the clinical profile of patients presenting with cervical lymphadenopathy.
2. To correlate the clinical diagnosis with pathologic findings in patients presenting with cervical lymphadenopathy.

Materials and Methods

The hospital based observational study was carried out in Department of Otorhinolaryngology, Assam Medical College and Hospital, Dibrugarh from March 2023 to February 2024. Patients of all age group and any gender presenting to the department

of otorhinolaryngology with enlarged cervical lymph node were included in the study. Individuals with pre-existing bleeding disorders or those experiencing cardiorespiratory failure, patients who are previously diagnosed with cervical lymphadenopathy and receiving some sort of treatment, individuals for whom fine-needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) and node biopsy was not feasible or was not performed, clinically non-visible and non-palpable nodes are excluded from the study. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee (H) of Assam Medical College and Hospital prior to conduction of the study. A predesigned case proforma was employed for data collection, comprising general information, history and clinical examination and investigations.

Figure 1: Tubercular Cervical Lymph Node

Figure 2: Non-Hodgkin's Lymphoma – Follicular Lymphoma

Figure 3: Extended Radical Neck Dissection

Results and Observations: In our present study of one year duration from March 2023 to February 2024, a total of 50 cases were included. The study found that the majority of cases (28%) fell within the 21-30 year age range, with 14 cases reported.

Table 1:

Age Group (in years)	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
1-10	3	6.00
11-20	5	10.00
21-30	14	28.00
31-40	9	18.00
41-50	8	16.00
51-60	5	10.00
>60	6	12.00
TOTAL	50	100.00
Mean ± S.D.	36.86 ± 18.14 years	
Range	5-78	

The study found a slight predilection for males, with a male-to-female ratio of 1.38:1

Figure 4: Gender wise Distribution

Other than neck swelling, the most common symptom was malaise in 50% patients followed by fever (44%), loss of appetite (26%), loss of weight (22%), cough (18%), pain (14%), dysphagia (8%), change in voice (2%), breathing difficulty (2%) and sinus formation (2%).

Figure 5: Presenting Symptoms

Most of the lymph nodes are less than 4cm in size; 54% of the cases had lymph nodes measuring between 2 and 4cm, 34% measuring less than 2cm, 8% measuring between 4 and 6cm, and 4% of the lymph nodes measuring more than 6cm in size. The posterior triangle group of lymph nodes was found to be the most frequently affected, which corresponds to 50% of the patients followed by upper jugular group (40%), lower jugular (22%), middle jugular (20%), submental and submandibular (18%), anterior group (2%).

Figure 6: Levels of Cervical Lymph Nodes

80% of the patients presented with unilateral involvement and 20% presented with bilateral involvement of the cervical lymph nodes. Majority of the patients presented as single lymph node enlargement which amounts to 60% of the total study population.

The lymph nodes in the patients were primarily firm (72%), with smaller percentages being hard (16%), soft (10%), or rubbery (2%). Most of the lymph nodes in tuberculous lymphadenitis were discrete (71.43%) and the remaining being matted (28.57%). 92% of the patients presenting with cervical lymphadenopathy had mobile lymph nodes. 6 (21.43%) patients had history of contact

with tuberculosis patients. The chest Xray findings were positive for tuberculosis in 3 out of 28 patients which corresponds to 10.71%. Most of the lesions (72%) were non neoplastic. Neoplastic lesions comprise of 28%.

Tuberculous lymphadenitis was the most common diagnosis, accounting for 56% (n=28) of the total. Notably, 3 cases of tuberculous cervical lymphadenitis also showed lymph node enlargement in the axillary region, indicating additional involvement beyond the cervical area. The other non-neoplastic lesions were reactive lymphadenitis (n=5;10%) and granulomatous lymphadenitis (n=3;6%).

Table 2:

Histopathological Diagnosis	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
Tuberculous Lymphadenitis	28	56
Reactive Lymphadenitis	5	10
Granulomatous lymphadenitis	3	6
Hodgkin's Lymphoma	2	4
Non-Hodgkin's Lymphoma	2	4
Secondaries	10	20
TOTAL	50	100.00

In the present study, 4 cases were diagnosed as lymphoma on histopathological examination. Further investigation with immunohistochemistry provided with 2 cases (50%) of classical Hodgkin's lymphoma, one case (25%) of low grade follicular lymphoma and one case (25%) of diffuse large B cell lymphoma NOS, GCB subtype.

Figure 7: Immunohistochemistry diagnosis

10 patients were diagnosed to have secondary metastatic cervical lymphadenopathy. Out of these,

6 cases were arising from the larynx, one arising from the papillary carcinoma of thyroid, one arising

from oral cavity (buccal mucosa) and one arising from the oropharynx (soft palate). The primary site of origin of one case is unknown and is categorized as carcinoma of unknown primary.

Discussion

The age range of the study population spans nearly eight decades, from 5 years to 78 years. The peak incidence of cervical lymphadenopathy was between the ages of 21-30 years. Pradeep KR et al [5], R NN et al [1] and Balakrishnan A et al [6] in their study found the maximum age group with cervical lymphadenopathy as 21-30 years followed by 31-40 years. The study's gender distribution revealed a slight male preponderance, with 58% of patients being male and 42% being female, resulting in a male-to-female ratio of 1.38:1, which is consistent with the findings of Gorle VK et al [7] and Nazma S et al [8].

The most common symptoms were malaise (50%), fever (44%), and loss of appetite (26%). Other symptoms included weight loss (22%), cough (18%), pain (14%), dysphagia (8%), and less frequently, change in voice, breathing difficulty, and sinus formation (each 2%). Jha BC et al [9] in their study found the maximum number of patients presented with malaise [n=10;17.8%] followed by loss of weight [n=8;14.3%], cough [n=6;10.7%], fever [n=6;10.7%] and discharging sinus [n=3;5.3%].

Pradeep KR et al [5] in their study observed fever [n=19;19%] as the most common symptom followed by loss of weight [n=17;17%], pain [n=15;15%], cough [n=13;13%], loss of appetite [n=12;12%], dysphagia [n=2;2%] and dysphonia [n=1; 1%]. Mukherjee A et al [10] in their study found pain and fever as the most common symptoms [n=9; 18%] each followed by loss of weight [n=8;16%], cough [n=6;12%], loss of appetite [n=5;10%], dysphonia [n=2; 4%] and dysphagia [n=1;2%].

In this study, we found the consistency of lymph nodes were firm in 36 patients (72%), hard in 8 patients (16%), soft in 5 patients (10%) and rubbery in one patient (2%). Most of the lymph nodes exhibited a firm consistency upon palpation.

Similar observation was made by Melkundi RS et al [11] with 78% of firm nodes, 20% of hard nodes and 2% of rubbery consistency. Guruswamy CH et al [12] also found majority of lymph nodes to be firm in consistency (77%) and remaining to be hard in consistency (23%). Bairwa DPK et al [13] in their study found a vast majority of lymph nodes to be firm (90%), remaining 8% to be hard and 2% to be rubbery in consistency. 92% (n=46) of the patients with cervical lymphadenopathy had mobile nodes where as 8% (n=4) were fixed. The fixed nodes were seen in malignant lymph nodes

especially due to secondary deposits. Melkundi RS et al [11] in their study found 90% of the lymph nodes to be mobile. Similar results were found in the study conducted by Bairwa DPK et al [13] which was 10% fixed. Guruswamy CH et al [12] in their study found 80% of the patients to have mobile lymph nodes.

In this study, we found 28 patients to be diagnosed with tuberculosis. Out of these 6 (21.43%) patients had history of contact with tuberculosis patients. The remaining 78.57% of the tuberculous lymphadenitis patient had no history of exposure to tuberculosis patients. The chest Xray findings were positive for tuberculosis in 3 out of 28 patients which corresponds to 10.71%. The remaining 89.29% of the patients had normal chest X ray findings. Jha BC et al [9] in their study found 16% of patients with tubercular lymphadenitis had positive chest X ray findings. Pradeep KR et al [5] found 9.4% and Mukherjee A et al [10] found 9.09% of the TB lymphadenitis patients to have positive Xray findings. R NN et al [1] in their study found 13%, Mukherjee A et al [10] found 22.7% and Balakrishnan A et al [6] found 12.69% of the patients had exposure to tuberculosis.

The definitive diagnosis of the cervical lymph nodes was made by histopathological evaluation after the biopsy of the specimen. In our study, 50 patients underwent excision/incision biopsy and the diagnosis was made on the basis of histopathological examination. Most of the lesions (72%) were non-neoplastic. Neoplastic lesions comprise of 28%. The majority of the cases were tuberculous lymphadenitis (n=28;56%), followed by secondaries (n=10;20%), reactive lymphadenitis (n=5;10%), lymphoma (n=4;8%) and granulomatous lymphadenitis (n=3;6%). Among the lymphoma patients, two were Hodgkin's lymphoma and two were non-Hodgkin's lymphoma.

Additionally, immunohistochemistry was performed on the cases diagnosed as lymphoma and were further identified as low-grade follicular lymphoma (1 case), diffuse large B cell lymphoma NOS GCB subtype (1 case) and classical Hodgkin's lymphoma (2 cases). Ullah S et al [14] in their study found the maximum number of cases to be non-neoplastic with 69% of tuberculosis, 18% of reactive lymphadenitis, 5% of granulomatous lymphadenitis, 3% each of Hodgkin's lymphoma & non-Hodgkin's lymphoma and 2% of secondary deposits. Rajhans AR et al [15] in their study found tuberculosis (62.5%), reactive lymphadenitis (10%), granulomatous lymphadenitis (12.5%), Hodgkin's lymphoma (3.75%), non-Hodgkin's lymphoma (2.5%) and secondary deposits in 8.75% of the total patients. In our present study, we have made a clinical diagnosis initially on the basis of history and clinical examination, which is followed

by the pathological diagnosis. The pathological diagnosis is again a two-step procedure which is initially diagnosed with cytological study (FNAC), and confirmed with histopathological study after biopsy. Here in this study, we have clinically diagnosed 31 cases of tuberculosis, 8 cases of reactive lymphadenitis, 3 cases of granulomatous lymphadenitis, 7 cases of secondaries and one case of lymphoma. On FNAC, we have done the cytological diagnosis of 24 cases of tuberculosis, 7 cases of reactive lymphadenitis, 6 cases of granulomatous lymphadenitis, 2 cases of Hodgkin's lymphoma & one case of non-Hodgkin's lymphoma and 10 cases of lymph node secondaries. On histopathological diagnosis after biopsy, we found 28 cases of tuberculosis, 5 cases of reactive lymphadenitis, 3 cases of granulomatous lymphadenitis, 2 cases of Hodgkin's lymphoma, 2 cases of non-Hodgkin's lymphoma and 10 case of secondaries.

Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) had a high diagnostic accuracy for tuberculosis (TB) cervical lymphadenitis, with a sensitivity of 85.71%, specificity of 100% and accuracy of 92%. In contrast, clinical diagnosis alone had a lower diagnostic accuracy for TB cervical lymphadenitis, with a sensitivity of 82.14%, specificity of 63.63% and accuracy of 74%. This suggests that FNAC is a more reliable diagnostic tool for TB cervical lymphadenitis than clinical diagnosis alone, with a higher accuracy and perfect specificity. The Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) test demonstrated high accuracy in diagnosing reactive lymphadenitis, with 80% sensitivity and 93.33% specificity, outperforming clinical diagnosis which had 40% sensitivity and 86.66% specificity.

The Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) test showed moderate to high accuracy in diagnosing granulomatous lymphadenitis, with 66.67% sensitivity and 91.48% specificity, while clinical diagnosis had lower sensitivity (33.33%) but higher specificity (95.74%), resulting in a similar overall accuracy (92%) to FNAC (90%).

The Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) test demonstrated perfect accuracy in diagnosing Hodgkin's lymphoma, with 100% sensitivity and 100% specificity; whereas for non-Hodgkin's lymphoma with a relatively low sensitivity of 50% and 100% specificity with an overall accuracy of 98% outperforming clinical diagnosis which had significantly lower sensitivity (25%) despite perfect specificity (100%), resulting in an overall accuracy of 94%. The Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) test demonstrated perfect accuracy in diagnosing malignant secondaries, with 100% sensitivity and 100% specificity, outperforming clinical diagnosis which had lower sensitivity (70%) despite perfect specificity (100%), resulting

in an overall accuracy of 94% compared to FNAC's 100% accuracy.

Thakur JS et al [16] in their study found the sensitivity and specificity for clinical examination in diagnosing the metastatic secondary nodes as 73.33% and 70% respectively with an accuracy of 72%. Suri AK et al [17] in their study found that FNAC demonstrated high accuracy (96%) for tuberculous lymphadenitis, with sensitivity of 84.6% and perfect specificity (100%). Excellent accuracy (98%) for reactive lymphadenitis, with perfect sensitivity (100%) and high specificity (96.9%). High accuracy (98%) for Hodgkin's disease, with sensitivity of 75% and perfect specificity (100%). Perfect accuracy (100%) for non-Hodgkin's lymphoma, with both sensitivity and specificity reaching 100%. R NN et al [1] in their study found that FNAC was highly effective in diagnosing tuberculous lymphadenitis, with a sensitivity of 95.4% and specificity of 83.3%; chronic nonspecific lymphadenitis, with a sensitivity of 93.75% and specificity of 96.66%, indicating excellent diagnostic accuracy. Sharma N et al [18] in their study found the sensitivity and specificity of FNAC on diagnosing the granulomatous lymphadenitis as 68.4% and 91.3% respectively with an accuracy of 77%. Moderate sensitivity (68.8%) and high specificity (88.9%) for diagnosing reactive lymphadenitis, with an accuracy of 83.6%. High overall sensitivity (91.1%) but lower specificity (60%), resulting in an overall accuracy of 88.5% for all conditions examined.

Conclusion

The presence of cervical lymphadenopathy can be an important indicator that helps healthcare professionals to diagnose an underlying condition or disease. It can be a symptom of various diseases, including both benign and malignant conditions, which may be localized or affect the body as a whole.

Younger age groups are more affected by benign lesions, namely tuberculosis and older age groups are more affected by malignancies. Clinical assessment alone has less sensitivity, specificity and accuracy as compared to FNAC; however in malignancy the clinical diagnosis shows a reliable accuracy. Open biopsy with histopathological examination was found to be the investigation of choice.

This study aids in providing the magnitude of the tuberculosis in the general population of our country and to take the necessary action without any delay for the treatment of the same. The results of this study provide valuable insights into the age and sex distribution of lymph node diseases, their common presentation modes, and the specific

lymph node groups they tend to affect. These findings can empower primary care physicians to adopt a systematic approach to early detection and referral, reducing diagnostic delays in cases of tuberculosis and lymph node cancers. This is particularly important for primary healthcare settings, especially in rural or urban areas with limited resources, where access to advanced diagnostic facilities for lymph node diseases may be scarce.

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